

SEASONAL INDICES OF ARRIVAL AND PRICES OF TUR IN APMCS OF AMRAVATI DISTRICT MAHARASHTRA, INDIA

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Abstract

The present investigation was undertaken to study the trends in arrivals and prices of Pigeon pea in APMCs of Amravati district with the objective to study the seasonal indices in arrival and prices of Pigeon pea in APMCs of Amravati district. The APMCs of Amravati district was selected purposively for the study. The Pigeon pea commodity was selected for present study. The secondary data were collected from 12 APMC's of Amravati district for the period of 15 years since 2006-07 to 2020-21. The data were analysed with simple statistical tools for fulfilling set objectives. Trends in arrivals and prices, seasonal indices, coefficient of variability, correlation coefficient were estimated by using appropriate statistical technique for arriving at meaningful conclusions. This study suggested that the Agricultural Produce Market Committee (APMC's) of Amravati district should provide sufficient grading and storage facilities which will help to get higher prices to the producers. Study also suggests that the seasonality of arrivals and prices of Pigeon pea in APMC's of Amravati district which helps for the farmer to obtaining the better prices in the market. Pigeon pea (Tur) grower should bring Tur for sell in the APMC's of Amravati district during the month of May to December to get better price for their produce.

Keywords: Arrivals, Prices, Seasonal indices**Introduction**

Red gram (*Cajanus cajan* lin.) is an important pulse crop originated from India, grown in the tropical and subtropical regions of world. It is also called in different names viz. Congo pea, Toovar, Toor, Togary, Glandular, Gungo pea. Red gram contains about 22 per cent proteins, which is almost three times that of cereals. Being rich in protein and relatively cheaper, a large section of vegetarian population of the country consumes it as "Dal" in cooking form. Its leaves are an excellent fodder for animal and stems are an important source of fencing fields.

In addition to being an important source of human food and animal feed, every Red gram plant is in itself a mini fertilizer factory as this crop enhances the soil fertility through fixing atmospheric nitrogen. Pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan* lin.): - Pigeon pea is one of the major pulse crops of the tropics and sub tropics including America, India, Australia, Hawaii, Uganda, Italy, East and West Indies and South-East Africa. Pigeon pea is grown on nearly 5 million hectares making it the sixth most important legume food crop globally. Over 85% of the world's pigeon pea is too produced in India (Patil R. 2013).

In Maharashtra state crops are generally marketed in regulated markets, these regulated markets are called as A.P.M.C. (Agricultural Produce Market Committee). Agricultural Produce Market Committee helps the farmer in disposing of their produce in the market smoothly by reducing the exploitation level and to promote fair trade by providing infrastructural facilities to farmers. It is necessary to study the role played by regulated markets to sustain the agri-business in India, Maharashtra and particularly in vidarbha region of Maharashtra. Normal area of Tur is 47.17 Lha, producing 41.37 Lt with a productivity of 877 kg/ha. In total kharif pulses Tur alone is contributes about 34% in area and 48% in production.

Objective: - To study the seasonal indices of Pigeon Pea in APMCs of Amravati district.

Methodology

This chapter includes the materials and methods used for the present study. It deals with the source of data, type of, data utilized, selection of period and statistical tools used for data analysis to achieve the objectives of the study.

The present study has based on the data of arrivals and prices of pulse crop pigeon pea in APMCs of Amravati district for the period of last 15 years i.e. from 2006-07 to 2020-21.

Selection of Market:-The study was based on arrivals and prices of pigeon pea in APMCs, of Amravati district, so that the 12 APMCs, of Amravati district were selected purposively viz. 1)Amravati 2)Dhamangaon railway 3)Daryapur 4)Anjangaon surji 5)Chandur

6)Warud 7)Morshi 8)Tiosa 9)Dharni 10)Achalpur 11)Chandur bajar 12)Nandgaon khandeshwar.

Selection of Commodities:-Pigeon pea commodity was selected for present study.

Sources of data:-The data required for this investigation were collected from the office records of 12 APMCs, of Amravati District.

Method of data collection:-The month wise data in respect of arrivals and prices of pigeon pea were collected from the records maintained by APMCs of Amravati district for the period of last 15 years i.e. from 2006-07 to 2020-21.

Analytical techniques:-Data were analysed statistically to achieve the objectives of the study. The simple tabular method was used.

Seasonal indices in arrival and prices:-

Seasonal variations are those periodic movements in business activity which occur every year and have their origin in the year itself Since such variations repeat during a period are repeat during a period of twelve months that can predicted fairly accurately. Seasonal index can be calculated in index form as a measure of seasonal variation. Seasonal index for each month was calculated. (Thombare A. P. 2013) thus specific seasonal index refers to the seasonal changes during a particular year. Seasonal indices are given as percentage of their average. Seasonal variations in arrival and prices were calculated by simple average method.

$$\text{Seasonal index} = \frac{\text{Monthly average of arrivals/prices}}{\text{Average of monthly average}} \times 100$$

Results and Discussions**Seasonal Variation in arrivals of pigeon pea in APMCs of Amravati district.**

The seasonal indices of Pigeon pea arrivals were worked out for the period 2006-07 to 2020-21 and are presented in Table 1.

The arrivals of Pigeon pea start hitting in the market from the month of December-January and continued for next five to six months. The peak period of arrivals is January to June. Due to large arrivals during this period the prices decline. The lean period is from July to October.

Seasonal variation in Prices of Pigeon pea in APMCs of Amravati district.

The arrivals of Pigeon pea start hitting in the market from the month of December-January and continued for next five months. The peak period of arrivals is January to June. Due to large arrivals during this period the prices decline. The lean period is from July to October. The prices were recorded higher from May to December. Most of the traders release the stored stock of Pigeon pea during this period in anticipation of making the profit. The seasonal indices of monthly average prices of Pigeon pea in Amravati, Dhamangaon Railway, Daryapur, Anjangaon Surji, Chandur Railway, Warud, Morshi, Tiosa, Dharni, Achalpur, Chandur Bajar and Nandgaon Khandeshwar

markets were worked out, which are presented in Table 2. It is observed that the selected markets the prices of Pigeon pea were higher from May to December. All the markets recorded lower prices in the months from January to April. During these months the arrivals were large which lowered down the price.

Conclusions

Seasonal variation in arrivals of Pigeon pea in APMCs of Amravati district.

The seasonal indices of Pigeon pea arrivals were worked out for the period 2006-07 to 2020-21. The peak period of arrivals is January to June. Due to large arrivals during this period the prices decline. The lean period is from July to October.

Seasonal variation in prices of Pigeon pea in APMCs of Amravati district.

The seasonal indices of monthly average prices of Pigeon pea in Amravati, Dhamangaon railway, Daryapur, Anjangaon surji, Chandur railway, Warud, Morshi, Tiosa, Dharni, Achalpur, Chandur bajar, Nandgaon khandeshwar markets were worked out. It is observed that in these markets the prices of Pigeon pea were higher from May to December. All the markets recorded lower prices in the months from January to April. During these months the arrivals were more lowered down the prices.

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Table no.1. Seasonal index of Arrivals of Pigeon pea in APMCs of Amravati district. (2006-07 to 2020-21)

Month	Amravati	Dhamangaon Railway	Daryapur	Anjangaon Surji	Chandur Railway	Warud	Morshi	Tiosa	Dharni	Achalpur	Chandur Bajar	Nandgaon Khandeshwar
Jan	129.29	248.06	176.63	257.71	210.97	224.18	237.66	287.49	382.12	198.14	255.75	222.52
Feb	261.16	298.20	234.26	202.80	239.08	179.18	196.57	228.01	191.09	238.50	201.34	208.14
Mar	200.46	142.25	167.74	223.51	185.19	226.70	210.16	117.18	187.97	154.81	172.74	170.09
Apr	153.22	130.53	140.34	134.56	175.59	159.85	145.22	235.56	127.34	141.18	151.46	165.62
May	144.52	114.28	129.08	95.43	99.29	136.32	125.53	79.55	93.57	141.02	143.98	93.93
Jun	110.48	109.11	130.40	86.16	105.63	89.01	86.87	67.71	67.84	122.02	101.86	100.31
Jul	54.43	64.23	65.21	72.00	62.65	69.48	83.45	57.23	63.01	69.56	70.84	77.93
Aug	42.76	60.11	52.57	66.05	60.28	52.27	52.37	72.04	47.32	43.60	52.85	72.48
Sep	42.81	25.73	42.58	41.24	44.49	47.55	44.86	34.30	24.05	39.48	34.10	48.31
Oct	25.99	6.05	22.51	9.95	9.46	8.62	8.31	13.39	12.23	22.79	8.07	22.15
Nov	16.99	1.03	19.89	4.40	3.13	2.67	4.95	5.13	1.66	16.41	3.80	7.59
Dec	18.23	0.44	18.81	6.18	4.24	4.17	4.05	2.39	1.80	12.49	3.21	10.92

Table No.2 Seasonal index for Pigeon pea prices in APMCs of Amravati district. (2006-07 to 2020-21)

Month	Amravati	Dhamangaon Railway	Daryapur	Anjangaon Surji	Chandur Railway	Warud	Morshi	Tiosa	Dharni	Achalpur	Chandur Bajar	Nandgaon Khandeshwar
Jan	93.50	96.58	88.18	102.89	93.79	94.64	94.64	93.97	92.00	92.93	93.75	98.09
Feb	94.61	96.75	89.86	100.49	95.49	94.71	94.87	97.58	93.84	94.41	94.79	99.20
Mar	95.24	96.82	90.13	102.46	94.26	95.41	95.18	95.27	94.48	93.70	94.72	100.97
Apr	97.95	96.44	93.83	101.52	99.22	97.74	98.71	99.17	98.69	97.86	98.47	94.67
May	99.39	99.40	96.35	104.08	100.24	100.45	100.44	99.14	100.53	101.42	97.59	98.31
Jun	98.73	99.44	94.54	102.48	99.77	98.68	98.76	99.57	99.17	99.40	98.57	97.47
Jul	102.30	102.04	98.22	101.24	103.10	104.07	102.48	102.89	103.10	102.14	102.57	103.38
Aug	104.78	103.43	97.22	100.46	103.59	103.49	102.94	102.68	104.65	103.65	104.21	103.57
Sep	104.74	106.72	97.45	100.08	106.40	104.34	104.71	105.36	104.02	104.77	104.97	104.06
Oct	109.64	108.70	99.60	98.39	108.26	108.81	110.72	109.19	104.66	105.22	109.40	107.26
Nov	103.40	100.92	96.00	102.22	100.95	102.16	102.30	100.11	103.59	104.74	105.34	98.16
Dec	95.72	92.76	158.61	83.71	94.92	95.50	94.24	95.08	101.28	99.75	95.63	94.85